

**Report
on
Seed Diversity, Germination, Plant Standing and Harvesting**

**PART-1
KHARIF SEASON**

**State Name: Jharkhand
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023**

Fig.: Harvesting of Moong Pulses; Passbook Number 01-0010

**Submitted To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT**

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Under the project

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population.

Seed Biodiversity Report

Time Period for Sowing: JUNE 2022

Sowing Season June 2022, Jharkhand											
Jharkhand, Re-Introduction of Crop June 2022											
S.No.		Crop Name	Variety Name	Type of Variety	Seeds In Bank for Re-Intro	Seed destroyed / damaged in seed bank 2021-022	Seeds from Haat	Seed from Market/ KVK	Purchase from farmer 022	Trial Plot and Reporting (Account No.)	Ditributed to Account No.
	Arhar	Arhar	Madhopur Haat	Local	2	2.5	0	0	0	012,	0
		Arhar	Chandan Haat	Local	2	2.5	0	0	0	004,	0
		Arhar	LRG 41	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Arhar	Ratan	Improved	5	0	0	6 kg	0	001,	3, 008, 006, 0032, 0035
		Arhar	NTL 30	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Arhar	Farmer Var., Sirsiya	Local	3	1.5	0	0	5 kg X 130 Rs = 650 rs (Badki Soren)	10	0
		Arhar	Farmer Var., Sirsiya	Local	3	1.5	0	0	0	14	0
	GroundNut	GroundNut	Jiva Soren	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Karmeli	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			K6*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			TG-37A*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Urad / Black Gram	Urad	T9	Improved	1	1	0	0	0	001,	0
			PU31*	Improved	1.5	1	0	0	0	004,	0
	Moong	Moong	Chandan Haat	Local	3	1	0	0	0	012,	12, 014, 018
		Moong	Pawan Kumar	Local	2	2	0	0	0	14	10,18,22
		Moong	Khoriparan Haat	Local	3	1	0	0	0	18	14,19,22
		Moong	Madhopur Haat	Local	2	1	0	0	0	10	17,19
		Moong	Sirsiya	Local	2	2	0	0	5 kg X 100 Rs (chandshekar) = 500 Rs	4	21,23

		Moong	IPM 25 / Virat	Improved	3	2	0	0	6 kg X 100 Rs (Rita Hasda) = 600 Rs.	001,	3,004
		Moong	IPM 2-3	Improved	2	0	0	0	0	06,	9
	Kudrum / Hibiscus cannabenus	Red Kudrum	Madhopur Haat	Local	0	0	0	0	80 Rs X 5 Kg = 400 Rs (Anita Soren)	1	0
		White Kudrum	Telwa Bazar	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ghagra / Vigna Sinensis	Ghagra	Chandan Haat	Local	2	1			150 RsX 1 kg (Sodagar Yadav) = 150	1	0
							0	0			
	Maize	Maize Yellow	Kanchan KVK	Improved	3	1	0	0		1	3
		Maize Red	Jasidih Haat var.-1	Improved	3	2.5	0	0	10 kg X 30 Rs (Rohit Yadav) = 300 Rs	4	009, 0024
		Maize Yellow	Jasidih Haat var.-2	Local	6	4	0	0	0	34	24, 29, 30
		Maize Red	Chandan Haat	Local	2.5	0.5	0	0	0	13	013, 015
		Maize Yellow	Khoriparan Haat	Local	3	1	0	0	5 kg x 30 Rs (khelo pandit)=150 Rs	19	28, 29
	Bajra	Bajra	KVK	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Bajra	Telwa Haat	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Bajra	Madhopur Haat	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Ragi	Ragi	Madhopur Haat	Local	0	0	0	0	1kg X 60 Rs (mukumn Hembrum) = 60 Rs	004,	0
			VL 379	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				Total	54 Kg	29 kg			6 kg @ 1200 Rs. MR. parimal Ji's Account		38 Kg @ 2810 Rs. Mr. Subhash's Account
					Total Seed in Circulation in June = 54 kg + 6 kg + 38 Kg= 98 Kg						
				Sowing Season August 2022, JHARKHAND							

Germination report:

Crop: Arhar

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,004,010,012,014)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	arhar	ratan	19/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
004	arhar	Chandana haat	21/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	
010	arhar	sirsiya	23/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	
012	arhar	Madhopur	17/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	
014	arhar	sirsiya	21/7/2022	29/7/2022				

A/c no 001 Arhar	A/c no 004 Arhar
A/c no 0010; Arhar	A/c no 0012; Arhar

Crop: Arhar, Urad, Moong, Maize, Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (Sadmuni Murmu)

Passbook.no 004	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination on 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
Trial 1	arhar	Lrg 41	19/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes
Trial 2	urad	Pu 31	19/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 3	moong	sirsiya	19/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 4	maize	jasidih	19/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	NO	
Trial 5	ragi	VI379	19/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	

farm no 4

farm no 4

Crop: Ghaghra

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001)

Passbook.no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001`	Ghaghra	Chandan haat	19/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	no	yes

A/c no 001 image
ghanghra

Crop: Red Kudrum

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	Red kudrum	Modhopur haat	23/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes

A/c no 001; Image: Red Kudrum

Crop: Maize

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001, 004, 013, 019, 034)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	Maize	Kvk kanchan	19/7/2022	25/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
004	Maize	jasidih	17/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	No	
0013	Maize red	chandan	20/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
0019	Maize yellow	khoripann	16/7/2022	23/7/2022	No	No	No	
0034	Maize yellow	jasidih	21/7/2022	27/7/2022	N0	No	N0	

A/c no 001; Image: Maize	A/c no 004; Image: Maize
A/c no 0013; Image: Maize	A/c no 0019; Image: Maize

<p>A/c no 0034; Image: Maize</p>	

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001, 004, 006, 010, 012,014,018)

Passbook. no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	moong	IPM25	22/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
004	Moong	sirsiya	22/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	
006	Moong	lpm 2-3	21/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
010	moong	madhopur	21/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
0012	Moong	chandanaat	19/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	No	
0014	Moong	pawankumar	20/7/2022	28/7/2022	no	no	no	
0018	moong	khoriapanan	16/7/2022	24/7/2022	no	no	no	

A/c No 001; Image: Moong

A/c No 004; Image: Moong

A/c No 006; Image: Moong

A/c No 0010; Image: Moong

A/c no 0012; Image: Moong

A/c no 0014; Image: Moong

<p>A/c no 0018; Image: Moong</p>	

Crop: Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 004)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
004	Ragi	Modhopur haat	23/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes

A/c no 004; Image: Ragi

Standing Plant report:

Crop: Arhar

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,004,010,012)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Arhar ratan	70%	0	NO	No	yes	no
004	Arahar Chandan haat	80%	0		No	yes	
0010	Arhar ,sirsiya	65%	0		No	Yes	
0012	Arhar,madhopur	85%	0		No	Yes	

A/c no 0010; Image: Arhar	A/c no 0014; Image: Arhar
A/c no 001; Image: Arhar	A/c no 004; Image: Arhar

A/c no 0012; Image: Arhar	

Crop: Ghaghra

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 001)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Ghanghra Chandan haat	80%	30%	no	No	yes	no

Crop: MAIZE

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 001)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Maize, Kvk ,kanchan	85%	40%	Leaf insect	No	yes	no
004	Maize,jasidih	75%	35%	„	No	yes	
0013	Maize ,red, chandan,haat	85%	40%	„	No	Yes	
0019	Maize yellow ,khoripanan	75%	50%	„	No	Yes	
0034	Maize ,yellow jasidih	65%	30%	„			

A/c no 0013; Image: Maize	A/c no 0019; Image: Maize
A/c no 004; Image: Maize	A/c no 001; Image: Maize

A/c no 0034; Image: Maize	

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,004,006,010,012,014,018)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Moong, ipm 25	80%	30%	Leaf red	No	yes	no
004	Moong ,sirsiya	75%	25%		No	yes	
006	Moong, ipm 2-3	85%	35%		No	Yes	
0010	Moong ,madhopur	70%	40%		No	Yes	
0012	Moong chandan	65%	35%		NO	yes	
0014	Moong ,pawan kumar	70%	25%		No	yes	
0018	Moong ,khoripanan	60%	20%		no	yes	

<p>A/c no 001; Image: Moong</p>	<p>A/c no 004; Image: Moong</p>
<p>A/c no 0010; Image: Moong</p>	<p>A/c no 006; Image: Moong</p>
<p>Ac no 0012; Image: Moong</p>	<p>A/c no 0014; Image: moongs</p>
<p>A/c no 0018; Image: Moong</p>	

Crop: Ragi**Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 004)**

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
004	Ragi Madhopue haat	70%	45%	no	No	yes	no

A/c no 04; Image: Ragi

Crop: Red Kudrum**Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001)**

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any diseas observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Red ,kudrum,madhopur	70%	0%	no	No	yes	no

Crop: Arhar, Urad, Moong, Miaze, Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. Sadmuni Murmu)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disese observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Arahar, lrg 41	50%	0	No	No	yes	no
Trial 2	Urad ,pu31	45%	25%	,	No	yes	
Trial 3	Moong,sirsiya	50%	30%	„	No	Yes	
Trial 4	Maize,jasidih haat	70%	40%	„	No	Yes	
Trial 5	Ragi, vl397	80%	30%	„	no		

Crop: Ghaghra

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
001	Ghaghra, chandan	29/8/22	8-10	25-30	Yes	30/9/22	3kg	white	Insect ,feaf

Ghaghra

Pod and Harvesting report:

Crop: Maize

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,004,013,019,34)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity(kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other velnerable factor
001	Maize. Kanchan	19/8/22	420	1	Yes. Leaf insect	5/10/22	45-50kg	Red	no
004	Maize jasidih	21/8/22	320	1	“	5/10/22	25-30kg	“”	
0013	Maize,red chandan	23/8/22	300	1	“	3/10/22	20-25kg	„	
0019	Maize,, khoripanan	26/8/22	280	1	“	6/10/22	30-35kg	„	
0034	Maize yellow,jasidi	22/8/22	305	1	‘	3/10/22	40-45kg	„	

A/c no 0013; Image: Maize	A/c no 001; Image: Maize

Crop: Arhar, Urad, Moong, Maize, Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (farmer Sadmuni Murmu)

Trail plot no/passbook no.004	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Arhar lrg 41	0	0	0	Yes.	0	0	0	no
Trial 2	Urad pu31	27/8/22	4-6	40-50	..	6/10/22	500gm	Black	
Trial 3	Moong.sirsiya	23/8/22	4-7	40-45	..	6/10/22	400gm	Black	
Trial 4	Maize jasideh	26/8/22	290	1	..	6/10/22	3kg	Red	
Trial 5	Ragi.vl397	28/8/22	80-85	2-3	no	8/10/22	1.5kg	geruya	

Trial no 004; Maize	Trial no 003; Moong
Trial no 2; Urad	

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (farmer Sadmuni Murmu)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
001	Moong, IPM 25	18/8/22	7-8	40-45	Yes, leaf insect	29/9/22	5kg	Black	No
004	Sirsiya , moong	24/8/22	5-8	30-35		28/9/22	4kg
006	Ipm2-3, moong	16/8/22	5-6	40-45		30/9/22	5kg
0010	Moong,madhapur	20/8/22	4-6	30-40		29/9/22	6kg
0012	Chandan haat	14/8/22	4-6	40-45		30/9/22	5kg
014	Pawan kumar	18/8/22	4-6	35-40		27/9/22	4kg
0018	khoripanan	19/8/22	5-6	30-35		30/9/22	3kg

A/c no 001; Image: Moong

A/c no 004; Image: Moong

A/c no 006; Image: Moong

A/c no 010; Image: Moong

Ac no 0012; Image: Moong	A/c no 014; Image: Moong
Ac no 0028; Image: Moong	

Crop: Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no.004)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
004	Ragi , madhopur	20/9/22	70-80	2-3	no	8/10/22	18kg	Black/red	no
